

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Table S1. Lags and Autocorrelations for genetic chain.

	Lag1	Lag5	Lag10	Lag50
V1	0.1513	0.0931	0.0599	0.0047
V2	0.2683	0.2040	0.1527	0.0244
V3	0.2924	0.1787	0.1069	0.0166
V4	0.0956	0.0417	0.0178	0.0063
V5	0.6078	0.5117	0.4351	0.1181
V6	0.5536	0.4271	0.3322	0.0800
V7	0.2984	0.2247	0.1752	0.0420
V8	0.4540	0.2608	0.1686	0.0345
V9	0.2915	0.1468	0.0862	0.0206
V10	0.0757	0.0379	0.0080	0.0102

Table S2. Geweke Convergence Diagnostic for genetic chain considering fraction in first window = 0.1 and fraction in last window = 0.5.

	V1	V2	V3	V4	V5	V6	V7	V8	V9	V10
Z-	0.62	-	1.44	1.31	-	1.65	1.82	-	-	-
Score	12	1.2074	33	85	1.4575	53	52	2.0178	2.1005	0.7640
p-	0.53	0.22	0.14	0.18	0.14	0.09	0.06	0.05	0.06	0.44
value	44	72	89	73	49	78	79	36	56	48

Table S3. Lags and Autocorrelations for residual chain.

	Lag 1	Lag 5	Lag 10	Lag 50
V1	0.8057	0.5426	0.4020	0.0604
V2	0.8620	0.6342	0.4711	0.0554
V3	0.7001	0.4024	0.2340	0.0209
V4	0.4502	0.2201	0.1091	0.0055
V5	0.9022	0.7744	0.6484	0.1673
V6	0.8089	0.6285	0.4850	0.1156
V7	0.5975	0.4430	0.3315	0.0754
V8	0.4383	0.2489	0.1588	0.0446
V9	0.2829	0.1353	0.0743	0.0259
V10	0.0920	0.0295	0.0147	0.0007

Table S4. Geweke Convergence Diagnostic for residual chain considering fraction in first window = 0.1 and fraction in last window = 0.5.

	V1	V2	V3	V4	V5	V6	V7	V8	V9	V10
Z-	-	1.02	-	-	1.48	-	-	1.98	1.80	1.42
Score	1.3168	55	1.3238	0.3702	31	1.7848	1.9175	62	30	69
p-	0.18	0.30	0.18	0.71	0.13	0.07	0.05	0.07	0.07	0.15
value	79	51	56	12	81	43	52	70	14	36

1 Table S5. Functional annotation of SNP (single nucleotide polymorphisms) with significant associations ($q < 0.01$), chromosome, and position associated for number of reproductive
 2 nodes (NRN) and yield (YL).

SNP	Chr	Position	q-value	Gene	Auto Defline	Gene Atlas Desc	GO	Organism	Trait
S1_1482495	chr1	1482495	2.77E-18	Glyma.01G014 900 (PAC:30542948)	Pthr21087:sf0 - inactive shikimate kinase like 2, chloroplastic- related	Coexpressed with genes in leaf specific coexpression subnetwork	Inactive shikimate kinase like 2, chloroplastic- related	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i>	NP
S1_1482495	chr1	1482495	9.01E-19	Glyma.01G014 900 (PAC:30542948)	Pthr21087:sf0 - inactive shikimate kinase like 2, chloroplastic- related	Coexpressed with genes in leaf specific coexpression subnetwork	Inactive shikimate kinase like 2, chloroplastic- related	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i>	NG
S1_1482495	chr1	1482495	9.00E-03	Glyma.01G014 900 (PAC:30542948)	Pthr21087:sf0 - inactive shikimate kinase like 2, chloroplastic- related	Coexpressed with genes in leaf specific coexpression subnetwork	Inactive shikimate kinase like 2, chloroplastic- related	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i>	HGW
S1_6439362	chr1	6439362	7.03E-11	Glyma.01G052 600 (PAC:30545005)	Pthr23257//pth r23257:sf366 - serine-threonine protein kinase	Differentially downregulated in ammonium leaf vs. roots comparison	Serine- threonine protein kinase // subfamily not named	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>	NP
S1_6439362	chr1	6439362	1.85E-40	Glyma.01G052 600 (PAC:30545005)	Pthr23257//pth r23257:sf366 - serine-threonine protein kinase	Differentially downregulated in ammonium leaf vs. roots comparison	Serine- threonine protein kinase // subfamily not named	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>	NG

S1_6439362	chr1	6439362	5.01E-06	Glyma.01G052600 (PAC:30545005)	Pthr23257//pthr23257:sf366 - serine-threonine protein kinase	Differentially downregulated in ammonium leaf vs. roots comparison Coexpressed with genes in leaf specific coexpression subnetwork	Serine-threonine protein kinase // subfamily not named	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>	HGW
S1_55230421	chr1	55230421	3.07E-10	Glyma.01G223500 (PAC:30545113)	Pthr12608:sf6 - gdt1-like protein 1, chloroplastic	Coexpressed with genes in leaf specific coexpression subnetwork	Gdt1-like protein 1, chloroplastic	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i>	NP
S1_55230421	chr1	55230421	1.14E-07	Glyma.01G223500 (PAC:30545113)	Pthr12608:sf6 - gdt1-like protein 1, chloroplastic	Coexpressed with genes in leaf specific coexpression subnetwork	Gdt1-like protein 1, chloroplastic	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i>	NG
S1_55230421	chr1	55230421	5.64E-03	Glyma.01G223500 (PAC:30545113)	Pthr12608:sf6 - gdt1-like protein 1, chloroplastic	Coexpressed with genes in leaf specific coexpression subnetwork	Gdt1-like protein 1, chloroplastic	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i>	HGW
S2_20673122	chr2	20673122	1.69E-06	Glyma.02G162000 (PAC:30508659)	Pthr21737:sf3 - polyglutamine-binding protein 1	Coexpressed with genes in leaf specific coexpression subnetwork	K12865 - polyglutamine-binding protein 1	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i>	NP
S2_20673122	chr2	20673122	4.43E-18	Glyma.02G162000 (PAC:30508659)	Pthr21737:sf3 - polyglutamine-binding protein 1	Coexpressed with genes in leaf specific coexpression subnetwork	K12865 - polyglutamine-binding protein 1	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i>	NG
S2_43903677	chr2	43903677	1.76E-05	Glyma.02G251800 (PAC:30511112)	Pthr24209:sf7 - protein da1-related 2	Coexpressed with genes in flower specific	Family not named // protein da1-related 2	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NP

						coexpression subnetwork			
S2_44089446	chr2	44089446	1.17E-03	Glyma.02G253 800 (PAC:30509296)	Pthr32227:sf66 - beta-1, 3- glucanase-like protein		Beta-1, 3- glucanase-like protein	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>	NP
S3_39204450	chr3	39204450	5.65E-07	Glyma.03G179 800 (PAC:30517125)	Pthr24078:sf26 8 - mamallian p58ipk-like protein		DNAj homolog subfamily c member 3	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NP
S3_39584080	chr3	39584080	3.26E-43	Glyma.03G183 900 (PAC:30517384)	Pthr10641//pth r10641:sf561 - myb-like DNA- binding protein myb	Coexpressed with genes in roots specific coexpression subnetwork	Myb-like DNA-binding protein myb // subfamily not named	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NG
S3_39584080	chr3	39584080	5.97E-03	Glyma.03G183 900 (PAC:30517384)	Pthr10641//pth r10641:sf561 - myb-like DNA- binding protein myb	Coexpressed with genes in roots specific coexpression subnetwork	Myb-like DNA-binding protein myb // subfamily not named	<i>Glycine soja</i>	HGW
S3_40231832	chr3	40231832	1.22E-05	Glyma.03G191 500 (PAC:30518728)	4.1.2.13 - fructose- bisphosphate aldolase / fructose-1,6- bisphosphate triosephosphate- lyase		Fructose- bisphosphate aldolase / fructose-1,6- bisphosphate triosephosphate- lyase	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NP
S4_7378650	chr4	7378650	6.13E-22	Glyma.04G086 600 (PAC:30488751)	Pthr22950//pth r22950:sf208 - amino acid transporter		Amino acid transporter // subfamily not named	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NP

S4_7469872	chr4	7469872	5.78E-17	Glyma.04G087 300 (PAC:30489693)	Pthr31513:sf1 - glycine-rich protein	Coexpressed with genes in flower specific coexpression subnetwork	Pthr31513//pth r31513:sf1 - family not named // glycine-rich protein	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NG
S4_7469872	chr4	7469872	2.08E-03	Glyma.04G087 300 (PAC:30489693)	Pthr31513:sf1 - glycine-rich protein	Coexpressed with genes in flower specific coexpression subnetwork	Pthr31513//pth r31513:sf1 - family not named // glycine-rich protein	<i>Glycine soja</i>	HGW
S4_8091230	chr4	8091230	2.29E-04	Glyma.04G091 700 (PAC:30489230)	Pthr24006:sf50 3 - traf-like family protein-related		K11855 - ubiquitin carboxyl-terminal hydrolase	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NG
S4_8091230	chr4	8091230	1.27E-10	Glyma.04G091 700 (PAC:30489230)	Pthr24006:sf50 3 - traf-like family protein-related		K11855 - ubiquitin carboxyl-terminal hydrolase	<i>Glycine soja</i>	HGW
S4_50760530	chr4	50760530	3.78E-15	Glyma.04G239 000 (PAC:30488563)	Pf00560//pf077 14//pf08263//pf13 855 - leucine rich repeat (lrr_1) // protein tyrosine kinase (pkinase_tyr) // leucine rich repeat n-terminal domain (lrrnt_2) // leucine rich repeat (lrr_8)	Coexpressed with genes in roots specific coexpression subnetwork	Pf00560//pf077 14//pf08263//pf13 855 - leucine rich repeat (lrr_1) // protein tyrosine kinase (pkinase_tyr) // leucine rich repeat n-terminal domain (lrrnt_2) // leucine rich repeat (lrr_8)	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NP
S4_50760530	chr4	50760530	7.20E-23	Glyma.04G239 000 (PAC:30488563)	Pf00560//pf077 14//pf08263//pf13 855 - leucine rich	Coexpressed with genes in roots specific	Pf00560//pf077 14//pf08263//pf13 855 - leucine rich	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NG

S5_1958113	chr5	1958113	2.08E-26	Glyma.05G022 300 (PAC:30524580)	Pthr31267:sf2 - dentin sialophosphoprot ein-like protein		transporter b family member 27 Pthr31267//pth r31267:sf2 - family not named // dentin sialophosphoprot ein-like protein Pthr27002//pth r27002:sf129 -	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NG
S6_44353358	chr6	44353358	1.56E-32	Glyma.06G258 500 (PAC:30551093)	Pthr27002:sf12 9 - inactive g-type lectin s-receptor- like serine/threonine- protein kinase srk-related	Coexpressed with genes in roots specific coexpression subnetwork	family not named // inactive g-type lectin s-receptor- like serine/threonine- protein kinase srk-related Pthr27002//pth r27002:sf129 -	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NG
S6_44353358	chr6	44353358	4.22E-03	Glyma.06G258 500 (PAC:30551093)	Pthr27002:sf12 9 - inactive g-type lectin s-receptor- like serine/threonine- protein kinase srk-related	Coexpressed with genes in roots specific coexpression subnetwork	family not named // inactive g-type lectin s-receptor- like serine/threonine- protein kinase srk-related	<i>Glycine soja</i>	HGW
S6_49937701	chr6	49937701	1.77E-34	Glyma.06G310 800 (PAC:30551379)	1.14.14.1 - unspecific monooxygenase / xenobiotic monooxygenase	Coexpressed with genes in flower specific coexpression subnetwork	1.14.14.1 - unspecific monooxygenase / xenobiotic monooxygenase	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NP

S6_49937701	chr6	49937701	3.98E-18	Glyma.06G310 800 (PAC:30551379)	1.14.14.1 - unspecific monooxygenase / xenobiotic monooxygenase	Coexpressed with genes in flower specific coexpression subnetwork	1.14.14.1 - unspecific monooxygenase / xenobiotic monooxygenase	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NG
S6_49937701	chr6	49937701	5.17E-04	Glyma.06G310 800 (PAC:30551379)	1.14.14.1 - unspecific monooxygenase / xenobiotic monooxygenase	Coexpressed with genes in flower specific coexpression subnetwork	1.14.14.1 - unspecific monooxygenase / xenobiotic monooxygenase	<i>Glycine soja</i>	HGW
S7_37686216	chr7	37686216	1.51E-10	Glyma.07G207 500 (PAC:30492710)	Uncharacteriz ed		Pf13456 - reverse transcriptase-like	<i>Arachis hypogaea</i>	NP
S7_37686216	chr7	37686216	5.18E-05	Glyma.07G207 500 (PAC:30492710)	Uncharacteriz ed		Pf13456 - reverse transcriptase-like	<i>Arachis hypogaea</i>	NG
S9_47005920	chr9	47005920	1.72E-15	Glyma.09G248 800 (PAC:30485355)	Pthr12375//pth r12375:sf32 - RNA-binding protein luc7- related		Pthr12375//pth r12375:sf32 - RNA-binding protein luc7- related // subfamily not named	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NP
S9_47005920	chr9	47005920	4.46E-11	Glyma.09G248 800 (PAC:30485355)	Pthr12375//pth r12375:sf32 - RNA-binding protein luc7- related		Pthr12375//pth r12375:sf32 - RNA-binding protein luc7- related // subfamily not named	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NG
S9_47249834	chr9	47249834	2.44E-06	Glyma.09G252 200 (PAC:30486124)	Pthr10293:sf37 - monothiol	Coexpressed with genes in leaf specific	Pthr10293:sf37 - monothiol	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NG

S9_47249834	chr9	47249834	7.16E-03	Glyma.09G252 200 (PAC:30486124)	glutaredoxin-s14, chloroplastic Pthr10293:sf37 - monothiol glutaredoxin-s14, chloroplastic	coexpression subnetwork Coexpressed with genes in leaf specific coexpression subnetwork	glutaredoxin-s14, chloroplastic Pthr10293:sf37 - monothiol glutaredoxin-s14, chloroplastic	<i>Glycine soja</i>	HGW
S9_47316303	chr9	47316303	3.66E-05	Glyma.09G253 300 (PAC:30486299)	Pthr10795//pth r10795:sf394 - proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin		Pthr10795//pth r10795:sf394 - proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin // subfamily not named	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NP
S9_47316303	chr9	47316303	7.13E-14	Glyma.09G253 300 (PAC:30486299)	Pthr10795//pth r10795:sf394 - proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin		Pthr10795//pth r10795:sf394 - proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin // subfamily not named	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NG
S10_4024882 7	chr10	40248827	4.39E-03	Glyma.10G168 300 (PAC:30475036)	Pf03080//pf143 65 - domain of unknown function (duf239) (duf239) // domain of unknown function (duf4409) (duf4409)	Coexpressed with genes in leaf specific coexpression subnetwork	Pf03080//pf143 65 - domain of unknown function (duf239) (duf239) // domain of unknown function	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NP

S10_4024882 7	chr10	40248827	1.93E-12	Glyma.10G168 300 (PAC:30475036)	Pf03080//pf143 65 - domain of unknown function (duf239) // domain of unknown function (duf4409) (duf4409)	Coexpressed with genes in leaf specific coexpression subnetwork	Pf03080//pf143 65 - domain of unknown function (duf239) // domain of unknown function	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NG
S10_4025104 2	chr10	40251042	2.27E-08	Glyma.10G168 300 (PAC:30475036)	Pf03080//pf143 65 - domain of unknown function (duf239) // domain of unknown function (duf4409) (duf4409)	Coexpressed with genes in leaf specific coexpression subnetwork	Pf03080//pf143 65 - domain of unknown function (duf239) // domain of unknown function	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NG
S10_4025104 2	chr10	40251042	1.53E-03	Glyma.10G168 300 (PAC:30475036)	Pf03080//pf143 65 - domain of unknown function (duf239) // domain of unknown function (duf4409) (duf4409)	Coexpressed with genes in leaf specific coexpression subnetwork	Pf03080//pf143 65 - domain of unknown function (duf239) // domain of unknown function	<i>Glycine soja</i>	HGW
S10_4025104 4	chr10	40251044	4.26E-07	Glyma.10G168 300 (PAC:30475036)	Pf03080//pf143 65 - domain of unknown	Coexpressed with genes in leaf specific	Pf03080//pf143 65 - domain of unknown	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NP

S10_4613717 6	chr10	46137176	8.66E-28	Glyma.10G231 700 (PAC:30474582)	Pthr11972//pth r11972:sf79 - nadph oxidase	Pthr11972//pth r11972:sf79 - nadph oxidase // subfamily not named	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NG
S10_4656114 4	chr10	46561144	1.44E-13	Glyma.10G236 800 (PAC:30475565)	Pthr11361:sf34 - DNA mismatch repair protein msh3	K08736 - DNA mismatch repair protein msh3	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NP
S10_4656114 4	chr10	46561144	2.92E-05	Glyma.10G236 800 (PAC:30475565)	Pthr11361:sf34 - DNA mismatch repair protein msh3	K08736 - DNA mismatch repair protein msh3	<i>Glycine soja</i>	HGW
S10_4656260 1	chr10	46562601	1.41E-04	Glyma.10G236 800 (PAC:30475565)	Pthr11361:sf34 - DNA mismatch repair protein msh3	K08736 - DNA mismatch repair protein msh3	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NP
S10_4656260 1	chr10	46562601	8.73E-12	Glyma.10G236 800 (PAC:30475565)	Pthr11361:sf34 - DNA mismatch repair protein msh3	K08736 - DNA mismatch repair protein msh3	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NG
S11_409949	chr11	409949	2.17E-16	Glyma.11G005 500 (PAC:30527972)	Pthr24098:sf10 - acyl-coa n- acyltransferase with ring/fyve/phd- type zinc finger protein-related	Pthr24098//pth r24098:sf10 - family not named // acyl-coa n- acyltransferase with ring/fyve/phd- type zinc finger protein-related	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NP
S11_409949	chr11	409949	1.50E-04	Glyma.11G005 500 (PAC:30527972)	Pthr24098:sf10 - acyl-coa n- acyltransferase	Pthr24098//pth r24098:sf10 - family not named	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NG

S11_416096	chr11	416096	6.55E-03	Glyma.11G005 500 (PAC:30527972)	with ring/fyve/phd- type zinc finger protein-related Pthr24098:sf10 - acyl-coa n- acyltransferase with ring/fyve/phd- type zinc finger protein-related		// acyl-coa n- acyltransferase with ring/fyve/phd- type zinc finger protein-related Pthr24098//pth r24098:sf10 - family not named // acyl-coa n- acyltransferase with ring/fyve/phd- type zinc finger protein-related Pthr24098//pth r24098:sf10 - family not named	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NP
S11_416096	chr11	416096	3.75E-03	Glyma.11G005 500 (PAC:30527972)	with ring/fyve/phd- type zinc finger protein-related Pthr24098:sf10 - acyl-coa n- acyltransferase with ring/fyve/phd- type zinc finger protein-related		// acyl-coa n- acyltransferase with ring/fyve/phd- type zinc finger protein-related	<i>Glycine soja</i>	HGW
S11_467613	chr11	467613	4.57E-24	Glyma.11G006 700 (PAC:30528321)	Uncharacteriz ed				NG
S12_4006314 4	chr12	40063144	2.41E-05	Glyma.12G242 300 (PAC:30548281)	Pthr11566//pth r11566:sf69 - dynamain	Coexpressed with genes in roots specific coexpression subnetwork	Pthr11566//pth r11566:sf69 - dynamain // subfamily not named	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NP

S12_4006314 4	chr12	40063144	2.58E-03	Glyma.12G242 300 (PAC:30548281)	Pthr11566//pth r11566:sf69 - dynamamin	Coexpressed with genes in roots specific coexpression subnetwork	Pthr11566//pth r11566:sf69 - dynamamin // subfamily not named	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NG
S14_1872929	chr14	1872929	2.29E-03	Glyma.14G026 100 (PAC:30532783)	Pthr11527:sf13 4 - heat shock protein 42		Pthr11527//pth r11527:sf134 - small heat-shock protein hsp20 family // heat shock protein 42	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NP
S14_1872929	chr14	1872929	5.42E-42	Glyma.14G026 100 (PAC:30532783)	Pthr11527:sf13 4 - heat shock protein 42		Pthr11527//pth r11527:sf134 - small heat-shock protein hsp20 family // heat shock protein 42	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NG
S14_2693732	chr14	2693732	5.57E-16	Glyma.14G036 100 (PAC:30533157)	Kog2425 - nuclear protein involved in cell morphogenesis and cell surface growth		K16912 - ribosomal biogenesis protein las1	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NP
S14_2693732	chr14	2693732	1.38E-30	Glyma.14G036 100 (PAC:30533157)	nuclear protein involved in cell morphogenesis and cell surface growth		K16912 - ribosomal biogenesis protein las1	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NG
S15_9792989	chr15	9792989	6.80E-08	Glyma.15G123 200 (PAC:30496639)	Pthr12277:sf58 - alpha/beta- hydrolases		3.1.1.23//3.1.1. 73 - acylglycerol lipase / monoacylglycerol	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NP

S15_9792989	chr15	9792989	1.04E-03	Glyma.15G123 200 (PAC:30496639)	superfamily protein Pthr12277:sf58 - alpha/beta- hydrolases superfamily protein		lipase // feruloyl esterase / hydroxycinnamo yl esterase 3.1.1.23//3.1.1. 73 - acylglycerol lipase / monoacylglycerol lipase // feruloyl esterase / hydroxycinnamo yl esterase Pthr21136//pth r21136:sf92 - snare proteins // subfamily not named Pthr21136//pth r21136:sf92 - snare proteins // subfamily not named Pthr18901//pth r18901:sf28 - 2- deoxyglucose-6- phosphate phosphatase 2 // subfamily not named	<i>Glycine soja</i>	HGW
S15_9994109	chr15	9994109	4.03E-03	Glyma.15G126 200 (PAC:30498305)	Pthr21136//pth r21136:sf92 - snare proteins			<i>Glycine soja</i>	NP
S15_9994109	chr15	9994109	1.17E-11	Glyma.15G126 200 (PAC:30498305)	Pthr21136//pth r21136:sf92 - snare proteins			<i>Glycine soja</i>	NG
S15_1016483 3	chr15	10164833	3.12E-18	Glyma.15G127 800 (PAC:30498787)	Pthr18901//pth r18901:sf28 - 2- deoxyglucose-6- phosphate phosphatase 2	Coexpressed with genes in leaf specific coexpression subnetwork		<i>Glycine soja</i>	NP
S15_1016483 3	chr15	10164833	3.91E-32	Glyma.15G127 800 (PAC:30498787)	Pthr18901//pth r18901:sf28 - 2- deoxyglucose-6-	Coexpressed with genes in leaf specific		<i>Glycine soja</i>	NG

S15_1016483 3	chr15	10164833	3.08E-05	Glyma.15G127 800 (PAC:30498787)	phosphate phosphatase 2 Pthr18901//pth r18901:sf28 - 2- deoxyglucose-6- phosphate phosphatase 2	coexpression subnetwork Coexpressed with genes in leaf specific coexpression subnetwork	phosphatase 2 // subfamily not named Pthr18901//pth r18901:sf28 - 2- deoxyglucose-6- phosphate phosphatase 2 // subfamily not named	<i>Glycine soja</i>	HGW
S15_1408445 5	chr15	14084455	2.44E-03	Glyma.15G163 800 (PAC:30497710)	Pthr12933 - orf protein-related	Coexpressed with genes in flower specific coexpression subnetwork	K14774 - u3 small nucleolar RNA-associated protein 25	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NP
S16_2313285 7	chr16	23132857	1.59E-04	Glyma.16G109 200 (PAC:30561412)	Pthr22780:sf13 - ap-4 complex subunit epsilon-1	Coexpressed with genes in roots specific coexpression subnetwork	K12400 - ap-4 complex subunit epsilon-1	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NP
S16_2313285 7	chr16	23132857	1.28E-03	Glyma.16G109 200 (PAC:30561412)	Pthr22780:sf13 - ap-4 complex subunit epsilon-1	Coexpressed with genes in roots specific coexpression subnetwork	K12400 - ap-4 complex subunit epsilon-1	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NG
S17_3045112	chr17	3045112	3.56E-16	Glyma.17G041 200 (PAC:30480988)	Pthr24221:sf20 5 - abc transporter b family member 11-related	Coexpressed with genes in roots specific coexpression subnetwork	Pthr24221//pth r24221:sf205 - family not named // ABC transporter b family member 11-related	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NP

S17_3045112	chr17	3045112	3.29E-20	Glyma.17G041 200 (PAC:30480988)	Pthr24221:sf20 5 - abc transporter b family member 11-related	Coexpressed with genes in roots specific coexpression subnetwork	Pthr24221//pth r24221:sf205 - family not named // ABC transporter b family member 11-related	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NG
S17_3045112	chr17	3045112	9.88E-05	Glyma.17G041 200 (PAC:30480988)	Pthr24221:sf20 5 - abc transporter b family member 11-related	Coexpressed with genes in roots specific coexpression subnetwork	Pthr24221//pth r24221:sf205 - family not named // ABC transporter b family member 11-related	<i>Glycine soja</i>	HGW
S18_7050498	chr18	7050498	3.63E-03	Glyma.18G074 300 (PAC:30554509)	Pf00397 - ww domain (ww)		Pf00397 - ww domain	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NP
S18_7050498	chr18	7050498	6.03E-19	Glyma.18G074 300 (PAC:30554509)	Pf00397 - ww domain (ww)		Pf00397 - ww domain	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NG
S18_7241593	chr18	7241593	3.03E-11	Glyma.18G076 300 (PAC:30557191)	Pthr11085:sf20 - nad-dependent protein deacetylase sirtuin-6		K11416 - mono-adp- ribosyltransferase sirtuin 6	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NG
S18_9020232	chr18	9020232	1.18E-08	Glyma.18G090 800 (PAC:30557463)	Pthr31963:sf4 - f11f12.5 protein		Pthr31963//pth r31963:sf4 - family not named // f11f12.5 protein	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NP
S18_9020232	chr18	9020232	5.70E-15	Glyma.18G090 800 (PAC:30557463)	Pthr31963:sf4 - f11f12.5 protein		Pthr31963//pth r31963:sf4 - family not named // f11f12.5 protein	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NG

S18_9020232	chr18	9020232	4.63E-03	Glyma.18G090 800 (PAC:30557463)	Pthr31963:sf4 - f11f12.5 protein	Pthr31963//pth r31963:sf4 - family not named // f11f12.5 protein	<i>Glycine soja</i>	HGW
S18_2247687 7	chr18	22476877	5.76E-14	Glyma.18G142 700 (PAC:30558007)	Pf00118//pf040 78 - tcp-1/cpn60 chaperonin family (cpn60_tcp1) // cell differentiation family, rcd1-like (rcd1)	K09498 - t- complex protein 1 subunit zeta	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NP
S18_2247687 7	chr18	22476877	1.12E-26	Glyma.18G142 700 (PAC:30558007)	Pf00118//pf040 78 - tcp-1/cpn60 chaperonin family (cpn60_tcp1) // cell differentiation family, rcd1-like (rcd1)	K09498 - t- complex protein 1 subunit zeta	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NG
S18_2247687 7	chr18	22476877	2.34E-03	Glyma.18G142 700 (PAC:30558007)	Pf00118//pf040 78 - tcp-1/cpn60 chaperonin family (cpn60_tcp1) // cell differentiation family, rcd1-like (rcd1)	K09498 - t- complex protein 1 subunit zeta	<i>Glycine soja</i>	HGW

S18_5364024 8	chr18	53640248	3.50E-11	Glyma.18G249 800 (PAC:30558078)	Pthr10795//pth r10795:sf365 - proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin	Coexpressed with genes in leaf specific coexpression subnetwork	Pthr10795//pth r10795:sf365 - proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin // subfamily not named	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NP
S18_5364024 8	chr18	53640248	9.54E-40	Glyma.18G249 800 (PAC:30558078)	Pthr10795//pth r10795:sf365 - proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin	Coexpressed with genes in leaf specific coexpression subnetwork	Pthr10795//pth r10795:sf365 - proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin // subfamily not named	<i>Glycine soja</i>	NG
S18_5364024 8	chr18	53640248	9.89E-03	Glyma.18G249 800 (PAC:30558078)	Pthr10795//pth r10795:sf365 - proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin	Coexpressed with genes in leaf specific coexpression subnetwork	Pthr10795//pth r10795:sf365 - proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin // subfamily not named	<i>Glycine soja</i>	HGW
S19_3641457 8	chr19	36414578	7.47E-16	Glyma.19G110 300 (PAC:30514506)	Pf01844 - hnh endonuclease (hnh)		Pf01844 - hnh endonuclease	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>	NP
S19_3641457 8	chr19	36414578	8.83E-22	Glyma.19G110 300 (PAC:30514506)	Pf01844 - hnh endonuclease (hnh)		Pf01844 - hnh endonuclease	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>	NG

Figure S1. Gene ontology (GO) terms for the Number of Pods. SNP obtained from Multi-trait association analysis (MTM-GWAS) considering a p-value<0.01.

Figure S2. Gene ontology (GO) terms for the Number of Grains. SNP obtained from Multi-trait association analysis (MTM-GWAS) considering a p-value<0.01.

